

Alternative to the generally accepted Λ CDM theory

- based on the static (Einsteinian 1917) model of the universe - with dynamic (growing) classical matter, without the necessity of dark energy (Λ)

Abstract :

Albert Einstein.

That name has inspired immense respect and great admiration in me since I was a child.

I'm just an ordinary person, just fascinated by the universe and all the questions we try so hard to find answers to. I watch documentaries about space and then spend hours thinking about what I just saw and heard. But I always arrive at the same inner state, a form of dissatisfaction and frustration, as if the current view of cosmology has missed something very, very fundamental. In every aspect there is a weakness, a gap, for which another (bizarre) theory is created as a patch. The universe is becoming a very chaotic and difficult environment in which it is becoming increasingly difficult to navigate, and the situation is not getting any better.

But this is completely contrary to **what Albert Einstein very much wanted (and predicted)** - that **the universe should be beautiful, simple and elegant, without singularities and expansion, without dark energy or cosmological constants**. In short, without all those similar upgrades and essences to make it all "work" somehow.

1. INTRODUCTION

As we all know, in 1931 there was finally a general acceptance of the classical Λ CDM theory, which is based on an expanding universe. The missing forces were replaced by dark energy and dark matter, which no one has discovered anywhere in 100 years, although it is supposed to be everywhere (including around us), over 90%. I also want to mention here that we are relying on a theory from the days when steam locomotives still ran on rails. This theory was based on the discovery of the first "correct" interpretation of a phenomenon called **redshift**. And so the times gave their blessing to this interpretation without further consideration of whether there was **another possible interpretation of redshift**.

And I want to prove to you today that such an alternative interpretation does exist and explains the universe completely **without the need for dark energy, without dark matter, without singularities and infinity, and above all without the need for expansion of the universe**. And I will also prove to you that actually **Einstein didn't need such an energy balanced universe at all** as he thought, he just missed that fundamental essence in the equations,

his lambda,

namely,

that matter grows.

Chapter 1 - Static Universe - a new formulation - with dynamically growing matter

While modern cosmology assumes that the evolution of the structure of the universe is governed by the expansion of space itself, we are exploring a very different approach: **a universe whose space remains geometrically static**, and all observed dynamical phenomena - including redshift - arise **from the time-dependent growth of the dimensions of classical matter**.

As I hinted above, this whole theory was based on 2 fundamental explanations at the beginning. It had to explain the observed redshift completely and without doubt, and at the same time create new mechanical and especially gravitational conditions for the universe not to collapse.

So I chose the easier one first, which is undoubtedly the correct interpretation of redshift here at this early stage of the theory. So I first searched the scientific world for an existing theory that relied on the phenomenon of increasing mass. To my surprise, I found rather soon that no one had yet dealt with such an idea. And if so, never in the context of a static universe.

Here I would like to point out that nobody is counting on a static universe today.

Everyone blindly believes that 100 year old dogma and even today I hear counter-arguments from all sides that even Einstein had no problem with the expanding universe. However, it should be added that his work dates back to 1902, when he wrote in a so-called "drawer", and he did not start to think realistically about the existence of an expanding universe until more than 20 years later, when the red shift was discovered by Mr Hubble and co. This was only, under the weight of "evidence", Einstein's final departure from the original static universe he had proposed in his 1917 theory. But he certainly never fully accepted it for the rest of his life (although he did "believe" in expansion).

Definition : Growing mass and redshift

A photon (light) is emitted at the observed distant object, which leaves the system at the speed of light, so that no time passes and thus it does not change for billions of years. Which is not true of the observer, for whom time passes in a standard way, and so grows (relatively) in the meantime compared to the photon. More precisely, it grows in geometric scale, or if you prefer, in volume (V).

$$V(t) = V_0 \cdot e^{k \cdot t}$$

where "t" is time and "k" is the mass growth factor.

This growth is manifested **at all levels**, both **atomic and galactic** - everything and everywhere is growing equally, **but exponentially**.

This **phenomenon then implies a redshift effect**, as **our telescopes, rulers, and even the seconds in the atomic clock grow with us** and the observed wavelength appears longer - a redshift.

At the same time, **neither mass (m) and energy (E) grows** with increasing volume of matter, which in effect means that **the density (ρ) of matter decreases**.

$$\rho = E/V \text{ (decreasing)}$$

This is another key finding that led me to step number 2 - **verifying gravitational balance**.

Note: The redshift is then generated by other phenomena, such as the mutual motion between the observer and the object (Doppler effect) and also by the gravitational curvature of the object space - in sum, however, both these values do not exceed 5% of the total value of "z" according to the calculations performed - for distant objects - and are therefore negligible

$$z \text{ (observed)} = z \text{ (doppler)} + z \text{ (grav)} + z \text{ (growth)}$$

Summary

decreasing density (ρ) is then a key factor in the equations for completely different gravitational principles - the gravitational force is "diluted" and **there is no danger of gravitational collapse**. This force then acts uniformly on all levels - from atomic to galactic

This effect is **fully explainable** within the static geometry of space and **without the need for any cosmological constant. It also eliminates the need for dark energy**. All key cosmological phenomena can be interpreted as consequences of the internal evolution of **classical matter, which grows geometrically over time (or the growth is exponential)**.

In this way, we reinterpret (**Einstein's**) **static universe as a viable**, consistent and observably compatible model of the universe - but on the basis of a new **dynamics that is hidden in matter itself**, not in space.

The original version deals with this topic in a separate chapter, but I now know (from further research) that this model is so robust that it does not need any exact equilibrium.

Chapter 2 - The Red Shift is not due to a change in space, but to a change in time

Comparison :

1. In the classical Λ CDM model:

- The redshift is caused by the change in the wavelength of light **as space expands**.
- The space between the object and us is "stretched" during the time the photon travels - this extends its wavelength.

Corollary: geometric phenomenon in space, **time runs the same**.

2. In the model under study (mass scale growth) :

- The space is static, the **mass is increasing**.
- Meanwhile we have "grown up" - we have bigger units (e.g. longer atoms, bigger meters).
- A photon that was emitted a long time ago carries with it a "small" scale - today we perceive it as "stretched" - a redshift.

This implies, of course, that the light from the distant system was **emitted from a faster system** than we have today.

Thus, in the model under study it is a **time phenomenon**, whereas in the classical model it is a **distance phenomenon**.

Now let's see how such a change takes place:

The main idea says that:

- Matter grows with time,
- And this according to the exponential law:

$$f(t) = e^{kt}$$

where $f(t)$ is the relative scale of mass at time t ,

and " k " is the growth constant

That is:

- lengths (e.g. atoms, meters) are increasing,
- and the **units of time (e.g. second) grow too** - because they are defined through matter (e.g. oscillations of atoms).

By analogy, **time also changes exponentially, depending on the growth of mass**.

Frequency is the inverse of time :

$$f_{\text{osc}}(t) \propto \frac{1}{f(t)} = e^{-kt}$$

Change over time (i.e., the "passage of time") is the mirror image of the growth of matter - exponentially, but in reverse. **The more matter grows, the slower time passes**

Let's summarize what all this finding means :

1. Time is not absolute - it is a measure

Comparison :

In classical cosmology :

- Time is a universal quantity - flowing the same everywhere,
- The duration of events is objective,
- The Red Shift says, "The event happened then - and today the light has arrived."

In the model under study :

- Time is relative to the scale of matter.
- The old events took place at a different pace than today (in the beginning time passed unimaginably fast, but also the curve starts at infinity, from where it decreases and approaches zero)
- The red shift is a manifestation of a change in our own perception of time.

2. No need to expand the compartment

Classical cosmology says :

- The universe expands → the scale of space increases,
- Infinities, singularities, accelerated expansion, dark matter and dark energy need to be explained.

The model under investigation :

- The space is static, curved and closed,
- All change is due to the increase in the scale of matter,
- Redshift, CMB, structures, all can be explained without expansion.

It follows that the universe can be permanently static - and yet "evolve" as its contents change scale.

3. The Universe may be extremely old

In the classic model:

- Time horizon: 13.8 Gyr,
- CMB = relic glow as first light emission
- Before that there was the singularity (Big Bang).

In the new model:

- The CMB was radiated tens of billions of years ago
- The universe is perhaps hundreds of billions of years old
- Matter evolves over an extremely long period of time

And you can say that they pay

"Time passes because matter grows."

Reflection :

1 . Where does the phrase "time passes because matter grows" come from?

This statement is derived from the new model:

- Where space is static,
- And change over time is only manifested by an increase in scale (e.g., length, duration),
- The "unit of time" (the second) itself is growing exponentially:
- Thus, everything that we perceive as the passage of time (e.g. change of states, oscillations, aging...) is due to the change of scale.

2. Does this mean that without the growth of matter, time would not exist?

It depends on how we define time. We have two different definitions:

A) Metrological definition (time as a measure)

- Time passes according to the oscillations of matter (e.g. the atomic clock),
- **If matter does not change** → there is no oscillation → there is no change → there is nothing to "measure" → **time stops**.

In this sense:

without scale growth there is no measurable time.

B) Geometric definition (time as a property of spacetime)

- Time is one of the 4 coordinates of spacetime,
- It exists independently of content (mass) - it is a property of geometry,
- It can exist even in empty space.

It would apply here:

time exists "potentially" even if nothing is growing - but nothing is happening.

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3. So what about it? Are the two definitions in conflict?

Not necessarily. On the contrary!

We can say that:

- Time as a **geometric dimension always exists** (spacetime, a parameter of space/universe)
- But perceived and **measurable time** (that which determines the dynamics of the universe) only begins when **matter begins to grow**. Or this phenomenon of matter growth generates "**material time**".

It follows, of course, that we have "2 time dimensions" !!!

Dimension of "**material time**" :

- Mass time passes (if mass grows)
- If the mass does not grow, the material time stops " $t = 0$ "
- In the beginning, it goes by infinitely fast
- So it's slowing down exponentially
- We ourselves are now the slowest expression of time in the universe

Dimension of **space time (non-material time, frequency time)** :

- It is fixed and static, so it does not slow down or speed up
- Since this time **does not pass at all**, " $t = 0$ "
- It is the frequency space for the transmission of waves
- **The frequencies themselves are a spatial prediction and have always been there**
- Frequency can be imagined as a train with energy on board.

And what applies to both together :

- Their mutual independence
- They are part of the same space
- So they're completely connected.
- Each has its own function
- Material spacetime is possible exclusively and only for values $0 < x < \text{infinity}$
- The frequency space-time is designed for the values $x=0, x = \text{infinity}$
- It is the perfect systemic solution to paradoxes
- Such an interpretation is "imaginable" even for human understanding
- Infinity "tamed and locked" at time 0
- Perfect environment for light distribution (like waves)
- Summoned = slowed down - "materialized" back into a photon by the human eye - receiver

*Note: In the original version on Zenodo there is a whole extensive chapter explaining the photon paradox - it was during the creation of this chapter that I discovered the existence of material time. **And also the condition that if matter doesn't grow, time = 0.** This condition is beautifully **confirmed inside a black hole, where matter really has nowhere to grow.** And we can thus explain very logically and elegantly why time does not flow there - **and from my perceptual point of view, this is significant evidence that matter does indeed grow in our universe.***

I mean:

"Time existed, but it was physically empty - only with the growth of scale did time in our sense begin to run."

Chapter 3 - Einstein's theoretical equilibrium of his static universe and its use for calculating the "k" - the growth coefficient of matter

I have been thinking of ways to interpret the growth coefficient as quickly and accurately as possible so that we can move forward in theory. And I've evaluated that waiting for experiments with physical matter is completely out of my hands.

(I propose an experiment at CERN with two identical particles, one statically anchored outside and the other orbiting at maximum possible time and speed - theoretically, the orbiting particle should appear smaller in volume at the end of the experiment compared to the other particle - it has "grown" in the meantime (watch the mass, it remains the same))

So I thought to derive this value at least theoretically. And I liked the idea of using the already calculated Einstein's lambda and converting the value mathematically into the equivalent of the value of the growth coefficient for our growing mass

According to the idea, let's try to add to the equation what Einstein was missing.

Then it is true that:

$$k = 0.124 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$$

I should mention an interesting coincidence here, since I first placed my first version of this theory on Zenodo on 12.04. (These numbers are closely related to Tesla's numbers 3,6,9) - to be explained in my next philosophical paper.

I am deliberately not giving the calculation to avoid additional discussion - I am not a mathematician, this result is a calculation under special conditions using AI (chatgpt) and is not necessarily correct - **it is to serve as a "zero k"** which is derived from the exponential growth function of mass and energy that Einstein needed to keep his universe from collapsing.

However, all calculations based on this coefficient so far indicate that it could be defined correctly.

Comparison of Δt by Growth Model (Exponential vs Linear)

Object	Redshift (z)	Δt (Exponential growth) [Gyr]	Δt (Linear growth) [Gyr]
Galaxie (z \approx 0.1)	0.1	0.7686304822929432	9.824046920821118
Supernova (z \approx 0.5)	0.5	3.2698799040981	36.021505376344095
Kvazar (z \approx 2)	2	8.859776521517013	72.04301075268819
Distant galaxy (z \approx 6)	6	15.692823782704139	92.62672811059909
GN-z11 (z \approx 11.1)	11.1	20.10649558550561	99.13356438283127
CMB (z \approx 1100)	1100	56.483662392924835	107.96636488822479

So I sampled distant objects from across the spectrum and used "k" to calculate both the exponential and linear models.

The first thing to notice is that the **exponential variant gives much more room for the evolution of matter at an early stage**, unlike the linear model. I would consider this a **significant indicator matter grows exponentially** (more fitting to classical physics).

The second thing that doesn't play in the linear model is the behavior of high "z" values. In our case, 1100. This is due to the high value of Gyr, which here hits its limits. (To give you a better idea, for z = 550 the result is 107.87 Gyr and for z = 2200 it is 108.02 Gyr).

So we have **further reason to believe that growth cannot be linear**. But this here is more a setting of the parameters of the equation, which I have chosen not to adjust for linear growth. The universe doesn't like linearity. **The most evolutionarily advantageous curve is the exponential one.**

Note : Here, I really like how we managed to eliminate linear growth from the theory, despite the (possibly) inaccurately set zero "k".

Well, what are the impressions from the first results of the exponential table?

The resulting values look very favorable, at first I was worried about the huge gap "z" in CMB versus other objects, but as you can see, the math function doesn't see this as a problem. On the contrary, it handled it extremely well.

The results can then also be interpreted as follows (if "k" is correct) :

- We are no longer limited by the light that has not yet reached us
- We're actually seeing the oldest objects in the universe
- There is nothing visible behind them (and it is not true that the light has not reached us yet)

And now I'll just add the best part - **we'll see the "end" of the universe**. Yes, indeed it is, we see the universe in all its glory in this closed static model.

Then you may wonder - are we really that lucky to be in the middle?

Yes, we really do!

But the explanation may surprise you now :

The universe itself is:

- homogeneous and isotropic - for any observer, anywhere.
- It is topologically symmetric
- **Everyone inside such a universe is "in the middle" (there is no middle)**
- It has no boundaries

Subchapter - Relic radiation (CMB)

It is a **perfectly curved space**, and that is why the CMB does not fly towards us from a distance of 56.48 Gyr, in a straight line, but it flies towards us for so long, and from all directions evenly. Understandably, in this model the CMB arises by a completely different mechanism than in the theory of inflation. At present, this initiation mechanism is not yet known to me, but it does not prevent us from proceeding further.

Here I will allow myself to make an insertion, since I am now intensively devoted to this topic:

What brought me to this study was an objection from an astrophysicist at the Journal aas who couldn't understand why we don't see "very old" structures when this universe is much older - tens of billions of years, possibly hundreds. I answered this question easily, namely that we do not see such structures, because they do not exist. The conditions for the birth of the first stars in those times did not allow for their birth.

In the model under study there is no Big Bang, but a **gradual evolution of matter** (but not slow - as we already know from the equation, time passes infinitely fast at the beginning), from elementary quarks to the first complex structures emitting the first CMB (here it is not classical light, but microwave radiation at 160 GHz). Simply, even in this universe, light has not always existed, it needs the existence of more complex matter structures and especially the brightening of the primordial nebular matter structures.

And this is where it gets interesting, because by repeated measurements we get the same result that the **CMB (relic radiation) is 56.48 Gyr old.**

Calculating the age of the CMB in our model universe

Parameters of the Universe :

- - The universe is static in space, but its mass is growing (volume of matter, density decreasing).
- - Time in the material dimension slows down as the volume of matter increases (exponentially)
- - The frequency dimension is stable ($t = 0$), the frequencies exist in it as a seed.
- - Light (and all waves) moves through space at a constant speed c .
- - The CMB is not 'primordial light' or a remnant of the Big Bang, but an ancient ripple created in the environment of molecular clouds.
- - The CMB was emitted about 56.5 Gyr ago (in our time), according to our estimate.

What we want to find out:

We want to verify or refine the CMB age estimate in relation to:

- **CMB redshift ($z \approx 1100$)**

- To our model, where the redshift denotes a change in the geometry of the mass, not an expansion of space.

- A function of time slowing down (exponential decrease in the rate of time passing)

Calculation procedure:

1. Redshift relation in our model:

$$z = (1 / f(t)) - 1$$

where:

- $f(t)$ is the ratio of the time rate at the time of emission to the present time rate.

2. Inverse treatment for $f(t)$:

$$f(t) = 1 / (z + 1)$$

For CMB:

$$f(t) = 1 / 1101 \approx 9.08 \times 10^{-4}$$

→ Time passed about 1100 times faster than today.

3. The relationship between time and the growth of mass volume:

$$f(t) = e^{(-k \times t)}$$

where:

- k is our exponential time deceleration coefficient (~0.124)

- t is the material time (current units).

4. Modification of the equation for calculating the emission age:

$$t = -(1 / k) \times \ln(f(t))$$

Observation:

$$t = -(1 / 0.124) \times \ln(9.08 \times 10^{-4})$$

$$\ln(9.08 \times 10^{-4}) \approx -7.004$$

$$t = 7.004 / 0.124 \approx \mathbf{56.5 \text{ Gyr}}$$

Summary:

→ The CMB was emitted about 56.5 billion years of material time ago

→ The result is quite consistent with our model.

This figure is also very crucial for us in calculating the total age of the Universe (see the following sections)

Of course, in this case the CMB arises under completely different conditions than in the Big Bang theory. In our model of the universe, the CMB is (very likely) generated inside an impermeable continuous nebula of molecular material, where the photons emitted are permanently trapped inside this impermeable material structure.

By the way, I've been looking for natural sources emitting waves at 160 GHz in our time, and strangely enough, the largest emitters in the universe are molecular nebulae of large structures - which is very supportive of the CMB hypothesis.

It is only with the brightening of these nebular structures that the accumulated radiation is released, which we now observe as the **first photon cosmic activity**, the CMB.

And since we know that we are in a completely inert environment in this static model of the universe, how is the CMB likely to move around?

We've considered several model situations, but the most likely seems to be its already multiple wave bouncing off the perfectly curved "end" of the universe - we can think of it as a stone being thrown into the middle of a round pool, and the waves gradually hitting its wall and bouncing off. This, of course, causes wave collisions and the wave breaks.

We consider that our space is a very clean environment, the wall of the universe is (in our model) extremely smooth and reflective, and that such a reflection will occur completely in accordance with the law of conservation of energy, i.e. that there will be no losses or deformations (conservation of Planck spectrum).

What is the Planck spectrum distortion all about? The CMB today corresponds very precisely to the so-called Planck radiation of a blackbody at a temperature of about 2.725 K. This is an extremely specific spectrum, almost perfectly smooth and without large fluctuations.

And then today we will observe exactly this homogeneous radiation as we know it, that is, travelling towards us, completely from all sides, with an even distribution.

And now I'll show a graph (still just an estimate at this stage) where we are now on the material time curve (calculated on the basis of $k = 0.124$), taken from right to left (so we have already left the hyperbola of extremely fast time) :

What the chart tells us :

- Taken from right to left, where on the right we have the beginning of matter/time
- That at the beginning of time, material time passed infinitely fast
- And we are now in "calm waters"
- And we're just at the "beginning" of the peaceful age
- Where there is enough time and space for the evolution of intelligence
- And we have now (with this new theory) received an "invitation" to the highest league of intelligence

Chapter 4 - The Black Hole

- What is the function (role) of a black hole?
- Why are the quarks so small, is there an explanation?
- And how long will the mass grow, will it eventually fill the entire space?
- Or before all matter collapses?

We now have the key to answering each of these questions.

Reflection :

I can't interpret the exponential growth of matter any other way than that it **will keep growing**. But what does that mean in the end, growing all the time? Space in this model is limited, unchanging, and cannot be enlarged in any way.

Will this mean that one day perhaps **matter will fill all space** and so **stop growing, causing time to stop as well?**

- So that's exactly the first of the reasons I'm sure it won't happen - so that time doesn't stand still. Not even then, even if it were only the relative - material time.

The second reason is the existence of even a single black hole in space, which **will never allow such a state**. And I will explain why below.

On the other hand, this raises the question (**another possibility**) that **matter will collapse** until it all collapses once it exceeds a critical size.

But **as its density decreases**, can such a thin mass ever collapse?

It simply can't.

This universe is **designed to be extremely robust**, it is indestructible at these levels, so it is also eternal. Which we'll show below.

So I believe that neither will ever happen. This universe is designed to deal with that fairly easily and (again) gracefully.

1. BLACK HOLE AND ITS PURPOSE

All my life I have held the view that everything in the universe has a purpose. However, I have this whole "purpose" area in the philosophical realm, and I keep it strictly separate from the materialistic one. And now I see that I may have been making a mistake.

Probably when I finish this materialistic topic and I don't know where to go next, I will also publish a philosophical publication, there would be some material.

But now it is irrelevant.

As I expressed in the first version of this thesis that a black hole could serve as a **decomposer of complex matter into elementary matter**, it fits beautifully here.

In this universe, a black hole :

- is not just the end state of the star
- acts as an **extractor of overgrown matter**
- and matter still has room to grow
- acts as an information repository (over the event horizon),
- it is a **decomposer of complex matter** into elementary matter (quarks)
- **the quark is indestructible here**, so it is eternal
- holds quarks within itself as material ready to begin a new material evolution cycle
- (probably by the FIFO method) emits this new matter by quantum fluctuation - *(currently I have discovered a completely different interpretation of the emission, but I will offer it only in the moment, if the original interpretation is challenged/refuted)*
- thus regulates the ratio of large and small matter in the universe
- ensures a balanced energy state
- and **will never let matter triumph over space**

The cycle is therefore infinite from this optic.

Exactly the opposite of the classical theory of expansion, where space is infinite and time is finite, in this model we have infinite time and finite space.

Here are 2 more wonderful things about this mechanism:

- since **a black hole does not pass time, it is constantly shrinking in relative terms** (by the definition of the equation, when matter does not grow, time does not pass),
- And for quarks, this again explains their small size (I originally proposed that quarks do not grow at all, which was correct to some extent), since **a quark enters a state where time does not act** on it in a black hole for some time, and so it gradually **shrinks relative** to other matter. And then it is emitted back to the beginning of the evolutionary cycle of matter. Therefore, the entire universe in this form is nothing less than the **evolutionary cycle of matter**. This is also where the theory of conservation of information is verified (I think and believe it is still the same quarks), because in this model **information is never lost, it is only transformed**.
- Now there is only one question left: where exactly do these newly born quarks flow? I think I know the answer. But I'll keep it to myself for now.

The whole mass cycle then looks simplified as follows :

Matter - life - intelligence

All 3 states of matter are then developed exponentially (*Here this is already an overlap into my philosophical work*)

Once I had this thesis complete here, I looked at a very important task - testing the validity of the law of conservation of energy.

2. LAW OF CONSERVATION OF ENERGY

Simply put . It is worth mentioning here that this universe works on a completely different principle than Einstein thought.

I have to admit that the whole system is designed to be extremely robust, a self-protecting cycle, but with huge margins.

Here I will leave room for calculators and formulas to confirm such a claim.

However, I offer this:

Energy and gravitational stability in a universe of increasing mass

In this section, we analyze one of the key aspects of the static universe model with increasing mass structures: how and why this model avoids the gravitational collapse that Einstein originally thought was inevitable without introducing a cosmological constant.

Energy density and curvature of space

In general relativity, the geometry of spacetime is directly influenced by the distribution of energy and momentum, described by the so-called energy-momentum tensor ($T_{\mu\nu}$). This tensor includes:

- mass energy ($E = mc^2$)
- kinetic energy and pressure
- momentum flux (e.g. particle flow, radiation)

General relativity field equations:

$$G_{\mu\nu} = (8\pi G / c^4) \times T_{\mu\nu}$$

shows that the curvature of space (left side) is directly proportional to the energy density and momentum (right side).

Model of growing mass

In the proposed model, we assume that all baryonic matter (atoms, galaxies, planets) grows geometrically over time, but their mass (and thus energy) remains constant.

This means :

- The volume of V bodies is increasing,
- the total energy E remains the same,
- the energy density $\rho = E / V$ decreases.

Implications for gravity

This decrease in energy density means that each object curves space less than its mass would if it remained geometrically compact. In other words, gravity "dilutes" as the geometry of mass grows.

Thanks to that:

- gravity is weaker,
- is not strong enough to initiate a collapse,
- the universe can remain in equilibrium without a cosmological constant.

Chapter 5 - The Age of the Universe

Before we get into the theory of calculating the age of the universe, I would like to mention the importance of studying and understanding the nature of the matter until it is fully understood. Being a material oriented person by nature, my forte is the environment of matter. However, with the discovery of the non-material dimension, I was forced to take a cognitive journey into the world of waves and frequencies as well.

I came across the definition here:

- **Planck lengths** (the smallest possible distance that makes sense mathematically and physically)
- **Planck time** (the shortest possible period of time that makes sense mathematically and physically)

I immediately realized one fascinating thing - that thanks to it **we are able to define the beginning of zero and infinity mathematically with absolute precision.**

That at the instant of the mathematical value of the Planck length, 0 is "activated".

And this is absolutely great news from my point of view, **there is now a fixed reference point at the end of the scale**, even though the scale mathematically (exponentially) ends :

- at zero - Planck length
- at infinity - Planck time

Immediately, **another important point of reference** was connected to this newly acquired information, **namely, the already well-known age, CMB = 56.48 Gyr.**

In general, we know that the CMB is extremely redshifted **microwave radiation**, with a value of "**z**" = **1100**.

In the classical Λ CDM model, the value 1100 tells us that **space** has been **stretched 1100 times** since its formation.

Whereas in our **model of a static universe with expanding mass**, it is a **time value**, specifically, the **object appears to be 1100 times smaller (the observer has grown 1100 times)**

So I was now very clear which direction I would now take -

to calculate the age of the universe.

I was thinking like this:

- we are at time $t = 1(s)$ - a second lasts as a second
- CMB is older by 56.48 Gyr and a second is 1100 times shorter (faster)
- Or by analogy, in the last 56.48 Gyr 1100 times slowed down time
- And we know that the CMB is far and away not the beginning of the universe
- The beginning of the universe is when :

t(s) = Planck time

Thus, we have to work our way through the function to the value of Planck time :

Calculation of Universe's Age (Simplified Summary)

1. Basic assumption:

The "length of one second" grows exponentially over cosmic time:

$$\tau(t) = t_P \times e^{(k t)}$$

where:

- $\tau(t)$ is the length of one second at time t (in Gyr),
- $t_P = 5.391247 \times 10^{-44}$ seconds (Planck time),
- $k = 0.124 \text{ Gyr}^{-1}$ (growth constant).

2. Today's condition:

Today, the length of one second is exactly 1 second.

Thus:

$$1 = (5.391247 \times 10^{-44}) \times e^{(0.124 \times t_{\text{today}})}$$

Rearranging:

$$e^{(0.124 \times t_{\text{today}})} = 1 / (5.391247 \times 10^{-44})$$

Taking the natural logarithm:

$$\ln(e^{(0.124 \times t_{\text{today}})}) = \ln(1 / (5.391247 \times 10^{-44}))$$

$$0.124 \times t_{\text{today}} \approx 100$$

$$t_{\text{today}} \approx 100 / 0.124$$

3. Calculation:

$$\ln(1 / 5.391247 \times 10^{-44}) \approx 100$$

$$t_{\text{today}} \approx 100 / 0.124 \approx 806 \text{ Gyr}$$

Final result:

The Universe is approximately 806 Gyr old in our model.

So, as we have just deduced, the **age of the model universe under study is 806 billion years**. That's probably a pretty extreme increase over the "classical" 13.8 Gyr, but there's nothing we can do about it. Nature intended it that way and probably has its reasons for doing so. However, when you think about what processes must have occurred over the course of material cycle times to produce even an atom (if not a molecule) from a quark, then you have to conclude that it's probably not just that. And even in that early phase, time was passing unimaginably fast, as if someone wanted to rewind that boring little song (metaphorically) on a tape recorder (oldschool).

I like this universe. And I like it a lot. It's logical, simple, perfectly coherent, elegant, and it's the best production system I've ever seen (I'm a quality engineer by profession, so I have, shall we say, a systems background).

And here is a look at what the final projection of our current "being" looks like. For better visualization I have set the time scale $t = 0$ to 1600 Gyr, in other words, we are in the middle of the cosmic cycle. I would now leave aside the controversy about the correctness of such a decision. Surely in time we will come up with a theory that will give us a much more accurate view of the matter.

Conclusion -

Einstein just wasn't lucky enough to be attacked by growing matter, as I am now, otherwise he would have very quickly and easily figured out the existence of material time in space time and could have triumphantly called Heureka. Without these two essential essences and without knowledge of the workings and especially the role of the black hole, he needed an extremely energy-balanced universe, which already at first sight seemed quite improbable.

References :

Fox Tomas (12.04.2025) - Alternative theory to Λ CDM - without the necessity of dark energy (Λ)

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